

Effect of Natural Calamities on Farming Profitability: A Case Study of Satara

Charulatha S¹ & Dr. A Geetha²

¹MBA II Year, Mother Teresa Women's University, Research And Extension Centre, Chennai

²HOD, Department of Management Studies, Mother Teresa Women's University, Kodaikanal

Corresponding Author – Charulatha S

DOI - 10.5281/zenodo.19815076

Introduction:

The banking sector plays a crucial role in the economic development of a country by mobilizing savings and providing credit to individuals, businesses, and industries. Among all banking functions, loans and advances form the primary source of income and are considered the backbone of banking operations. Through effective lending, banks promote entrepreneurship, industrial growth, and financial stability.

Indian Overseas Bank (IOB), a leading public sector bank in India, offers a wide range of loan and credit facilities to meet the diverse financial needs of customers. Its lending portfolio includes personal loans, housing loans, education loans, agricultural loans, MSME finance, and corporate advances. These credit facilities are provided after careful evaluation of borrower eligibility, risk assessment, and compliance with regulatory guidelines.

Proper management of loans and advances is essential for maintaining profitability and reducing non-performing assets (NPAs). Indian Overseas Bank follows structured credit appraisal, monitoring, and recovery procedures to ensure the quality of its assets and sustainable growth.

This internship project titled “A Study on Loans and Advances in Indian Overseas Bank” aims to analyse the types, procedures,

performance, and significance of loans and advances in the bank. The study helps in understanding the practical aspects of credit management and highlights the role of lending in supporting economic development and financial inclusion.

Types Of Loans And Advances In IOB:

Indian Overseas Bank provides a wide range of loan and credit facilities to meet the financial needs of individuals, businesses, and other sectors of the economy. These loans and advances can be broadly classified as follows:

a. Retail Loans:

These loans are provided to individual customers for personal purposes:

- Home Loans – For purchase, construction, or renovation of houses.
- Vehicle Loans – For purchase of two-wheelers and four-wheelers.
- Education Loans – To support higher education in India and abroad.
- Personal Loans – For medical expenses, travel, or other personal needs.
- Gold Loans – Loans against gold ornaments.

b. Agricultural Loans:

These loans are granted to farmers and agricultural enterprises:

- Crop loans
- Kisan Credit Card (KCC) loans

- Loans for purchase of agricultural equipment
- Allied agricultural activities financing

c. MSME Loans:

Loans provided to Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises for:

- Working capital requirements
- Purchase of machinery
- Business expansion
- Trade and service activities
- IOB MSME Easy Loan
- MSME Insta Fund
- IOB TEJAS
- IOB Mahila Samridhi
- MSME Commercial Vehicle loan

d. Corporate Loans:

These are large credit facilities provided to companies and industries for:

- Project financing
- Infrastructure development
- Term loans for expansion
- Working capital finance

e. Priority Sector Loans:

As per RBI norms, the bank provides loans to priority sectors such as:

- Agriculture
- MSMEs
- Education
- Housing
- Weaker sections of society

f. Advances in the Form of Credit Facilities:

- Cash Credit (CC)
- Overdraft (OD)
- Bills Discounting
- Demand Loans

Loan Policies And Guidelines:

Loan policies and guidelines refer to the rules, principles, and procedures followed by a bank while granting loans and advances. These policies ensure that lending is done safely, profitably, and in accordance with regulatory norms.

• Compliance with RBI Guidelines:

Banks follow the rules and regulations issued by the Reserve Bank of India (RBI), including priority sector lending norms, interest rate policies, and asset classification standards.

• Credit Appraisal Policy:

Before sanctioning a loan, the bank carefully evaluates the borrower's repayment capacity, income, financial statements, credit history (CIBIL score), and purpose of the loan.

• Security and Collateral Norms:

Banks require adequate security or collateral to minimize risk. The value of the security is assessed to ensure it covers the loan amount.

• Loan Eligibility Criteria:

Each type of loan has specific eligibility conditions such as age limit, income level, employment status, business stability, and documentation requirements.

• Interest Rate Policy:

Interest rates are fixed based on RBI regulations, repo rate changes, credit risk, and the bank's internal policies. Rates may be fixed or floating.

• Documentation and Legal Formalities:

Proper agreements, loan documents, and legal verification must be completed before loan disbursement.

• Monitoring and Recovery Guidelines:

After disbursement, banks regularly monitor loan accounts to ensure timely repayment. In case of default, recovery procedures are followed as per banking laws.

• Risk Management Policy:

Banks follow risk assessment and internal control systems to reduce credit risk and prevent the rise of Non-Performing Assets (NPAs).

Aim of the Study:

The aim of this study is to examine and analyse the loans and advances system of Indian Overseas Bank, focusing on its policies and procedures.

Objectives of the Study:

- To study the concept and importance of loans and advances in Indian Overseas Bank.
- To analyse the different types of loans and advances provided by Indian Overseas Bank.
- To examine the procedures and policies followed by the bank in granting loans and advances.
- To analyse the performance of loans and advances and their contribution to the bank's profitability.
- To identify the challenges faced by the bank in managing loans and advances, including non-performing assets (NPAs).

Scope of the Study:

The scope of this study is limited to analyzing the loans and advances system of Indian Overseas Bank. The study covers various aspects such as types of loans offered, loan sanctioning procedures, credit appraisal system, disbursement process, repayment and recovery mechanisms, and risk management practices. The study focuses on understanding the bank's lending policies and guidelines in accordance with RBI norms. The analysis is based on available data, bank records, and practical exposure gained during the internship period. The study is confined to a specific branch or selected period and does not cover the entire banking operations of Indian Overseas Bank.

Need of the Study:

The study on loans and advances in Indian Overseas Bank is necessary because lending is the core activity and major source of income for the bank. Understanding how loans are sanctioned, disbursed, monitored, and recovered helps in analyzing the efficiency and effectiveness of the bank's credit management system. This study is important to evaluate the performance of loans and advances and to understand their contribution to profitability and financial stability. Furthermore, the study provides practical knowledge about banking operations and bridges the gap between theoretical learning and real-world banking practices. It enhances the understanding of lending policies, RBI guidelines, and risk management techniques followed in public sector banks.

Research Methodology:

The research methodology adopted for this study follows a systematic and structured approach to ensure reliable results. Both theoretical knowledge and practical exposure gained during the internship were considered while collecting data. Information was gathered carefully from primary and secondary sources to maintain accuracy and relevance to the topic.

Observation of daily banking activities helped in understanding the practical implementation of loan policies, credit appraisal procedures, documentation, and recovery practices. Discussions with bank officials provided additional insights into risk management and control of Non-Performing Assets (NPAs). The study was conducted objectively, and confidential information was used only for academic purposes. Overall, the methodology ensures proper analysis of loans and advances and supports meaningful findings and conclusions.

Research Design :

Research design is the overall plan or framework used to conduct the research study. It explains how data will be collected, measured, and analyzed to achieve the objectives of the study. In this project, the research design helps in studying the loans and advances system of Indian Overseas Bank and evaluating its performance and impact.

a. Research Objectives:**Primary objective:**

To evaluate the performance and effectiveness of loans and advances operations in IOB specifically confined to Nesapakkam branch.

b. Research Design / Approach:

A mixed-methods approach (convergent design) combining quantitative and qualitative methods:

Quantitative: analysis of branch-level loan portfolio data, structured customer survey.

Qualitative: semi-structured interviews with branch managers, credit officers and recovery officers; observations of loan-processing workflow.

This gives both breadth (numbers, trends) and depth (why and how).

c. Population and Sampling:**Population 1000****Sampling technique: Convenient and Purposive**

The sample was collected from customers of the bank who have availed various loan facilities. The non-probability sampling technique comprising of both convenience and purposive sampling were adopted.

Convenience Sampling:

Under Convenience Sampling, customers who visited the branch during the data collection period and were willing to respond were selected. This method was suitable due to time constraints and easy accessibility of respondents. It helped in gathering practical information about customer satisfaction, loan procedures, documentation process and service quality.

Purposive Sampling:

Under Purposive Sampling, customers who had specific knowledge or direct experience with loan and advance facilities (such as housing loans, business loans, or personal loans) were intentionally selected. These respondents were chosen because their experience was directly relevant to the objectives of the study.

d. Sample Size:

The sample size for this study consists of 85 respondents from the Nesapakkam branch of Indian Overseas Bank. These respondents were customers who had availed different types of loans and advances. The selected sample size was considered sufficient to collect reliable information and understand customer opinions regarding the bank's loan services.

e. Data Sources & Instruments:**Primary data:**

- Structured questionnaire
- Interview guides for bank staff (semi-structured)
- Observation checklist (loan processing stages & documentation flow)

Analysis**1. Chi Square:**

The Chi-square test is a statistical method used to examine whether there is a significant

relationship between two categorical variables. It compares the observed data with the expected data to see if any difference exists. This test is commonly used in research studies to test hypotheses and analyse survey data.

Null Hypothesis (H_0):

There is no significant relationship between the satisfaction with post-loan services and the likelihood of recommending Indian Overseas Bank's loan services to others.

Alternative Hypothesis (H_1):

There is a significant relationship between the satisfaction with post-loan services and the likelihood of recommending Indian Overseas Bank's loan services to others.

How satisfied are you with post-loan services	15	35	34	1	0
How likely are you to recommend IOB's loan services to others	27	42	15	1	0

Formula:

$$E = \frac{RT \times CT}{GT}$$

Calculations:

(i)

$$E = \frac{85 \times 42}{170}$$

$$E = 21$$

(ii)

$$E = \frac{85 \times 77}{170}$$

$$E = 38.5$$

(iii)

$$E = \frac{85 \times 49}{170}$$

$$E = 25.6$$

(iv)

$$E = \frac{85 \times 2}{170}$$

$$E = 1$$

(v)

$$E = \frac{85 \times 0}{170}$$

$$E = 0$$

O_i	E_i	$O_i - E_i$	$(O_i - E_i)^2$	$\frac{(O_i - E_i)}{E_i}$
15	21	-6	36	1.71
35	38.5	-3.5	12.25	0.31
34	25.6	8.4	70.56	2.75
1	1	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0
27	21	6	36	1.71
42	38.5	3.5	12.25	0.31
15	25.6	-10.6	112.36	0.43
1	1	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0
170	172.2	8.2	279.42	7.22

Formula:

$$\chi^2 = \sum \frac{(O_i - E_i)^2}{E_i}$$

Calculated Value:

$$C.V = 7.22$$

Degree of Freedom:

$$r = (C-1)(R-1)$$

$$= (5-1)(2-1)$$

$$= 4 \times 1$$

$$= 4$$

level of significance=0.05

Table Value (T.V):

T.V = 9.49

Conclusion:

The calculated Chi-square value (C.V) is 7.22 and the table value (T.V) at 5% level of significance with 4 degrees of freedom is 9.49. Since the calculated value is less than the table value ($7.22 < 9.49$), the **null hypothesis (H_0) is accepted** and the **alternative hypothesis (H_1) is rejected**.

Hence, there is **no significant relationship between the variables** considered in this study.

2. F-Test

The F-test is a statistical method used to compare the variances of two or more groups to determine whether they are significantly different. It helps to test the overall significance of a model or the relationship between variables. The F-test is commonly used in statistical analysis and research studies.

Null Hypothesis (H_0):

There is no significant relationship between the guidance provided by the bank in choosing the right loan product and the overall satisfaction with loan services of Indian Overseas Bank.

Alternative Hypothesis (H_1):

There is a significant relationship between the guidance provided by the bank in choosing the right loan product and the overall satisfaction with loan services of Indian Overseas Bank.

Did the bank provide proper guidance in choosing the right loan product	83	2	0	0	0
Overall, how satisfied are you with IOB's loan services	18	45	22	0	0

Formula:

$$f = \frac{s_1^2}{s_2^2}$$

$$s_1^2 = \frac{\sum \chi^2}{N_1 - 1}$$

$$s_2^2 = \frac{\sum y^2}{N_2 - 1}$$

x	x ²	y	y ²
83	6889	18	324
2	4	45	2025
0	0	22	484
0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0
85	6893	85	2833

Calculation:

$$\bar{x} = \frac{85}{2} = 42.5$$

$$\bar{y} = \frac{85}{5} = 17$$

$$s_1^2 = \frac{\sum \chi^2}{N_1 - 1}$$

$$= \frac{6893}{2 - 1}$$

$$= \frac{6893}{1}$$

$$= 6893$$

$$s_2^2 = \frac{\sum y^2}{N_2 - 1}$$

$$= \frac{2833}{5-1}$$

$$= \frac{2833}{4}$$

$$= 708.25$$

$$f = \frac{s_1^2}{s_2^2}$$

$$= \frac{6893}{708.25}$$

Calculated Value (F) = 9.73

$$V_1 = N_{\text{high}} - 1$$

$$= 2 - 1$$

$$= 1$$

$$V_2 = N_{\text{high}} - 1$$

$$= 5 - 1$$

$$= 4$$

$$V_1 = 1, V_2 = 4$$

Tabulated Value = 7.71

Conclusion (F-Test):

The calculated F value (9.73) is greater than the tabulated value (7.71) at the 0.05 level of significance with degrees of freedom. Therefore, the **null hypothesis (H₀) is rejected** and the **alternative hypothesis (H₁) is accepted**. This indicates that there is a **significant relationship between the guidance provided by the bank in choosing the right loan product and the overall satisfaction with loan services of Indian Overseas Bank**. Hence, proper guidance from the bank plays an important role in influencing customers' satisfaction with loan services.

Findings:

- The majority (69%) belong to the 26–40 age group, indicating that middle-aged individuals form the largest part of the study. Therefore, it can be concluded that the study is mainly

dominated by respondents in the 26–40 age category.

- The majority of respondents are salaried employees (57%) Thus, salaried employees form the largest occupational group in the study.
- The majority of respondents are undergraduates (62%), forming the largest educational group in the study. Hence, most respondents have completed undergraduate education, indicating a fairly educated study population.
- **All 85 respondents (100%)** reported that they **did not face any difficulty in repaying the loan**. This shows that the respondents are able to manage their loan repayments properly, indicating a satisfactory repayment experience with the bank.
- The majority of respondents (86%) are aware of loan schemes provided by other banks. This shows that the majority of respondents have knowledge about loan facilities offered by other banks, indicating a good level of awareness among customers.
- 83 respondents (98%) stated that the bank provided proper guidance while selecting the loan product. This indicates that the majority of customers are satisfied with the guidance provided by the bank.
- 62% of the respondents (53) stated that the documentation process is easy. indicating that most customers find the documentation process convenient.
- 62% of the respondents (53) stated that the bank staff clearly explained the loan charges. This indicates that most respondents received explanations about the loan-related charges from the bank staff.
- 41% of the respondents (35) are satisfied with post-loan services provided by Indian Overseas Bank (IOB). This indicates that

most customers are generally satisfied with IOB's post-loan services.

- 66% of the respondents (56) stated that they clearly understand the EMI structure and interest calculation. This indicates that most respondents have a clear understanding of their loan repayment structure.
- 26% of the respondents (22) feel that the documentation process needs improvement. This indicates that documentation process and transparency are the main areas that require improvement.

Conclusion:

The study on loans and advances in Indian Overseas Bank reveals that loans are an important financial service that helps individuals and businesses meet their financial requirements. The analysis shows that many customers prefer the bank because of its reasonable interest rates, trust, and the availability of different loan schemes such as personal, housing, vehicle, and gold loans. Most respondents expressed satisfaction with the bank's loan facilities, staff guidance, and the support provided during the loan process.

However, the study also indicates that there is scope for improvement in certain areas such as reducing the time taken for loan approval and simplifying the documentation procedures. Enhancing customer awareness about different loan products and improving service efficiency can further increase customer satisfaction. Overall, the loans and advances provided by Indian Overseas Bank play a significant role in supporting customers

financially and maintaining a positive relationship with them.

Reference:

1. Sharma, R. (2020): Credit Growth and Profitability of Public Sector Banks
2. Iyer, M. (2020): Loan Portfolio Management in Public Sector Banks
3. Reddy, K. S. (2020): Credit Appraisal Systems and Asset Quality
4. Kumar, A. (2020): Priority Sector Lending and Credit Risk
5. Verma, S. (2020): Loan Recovery Management Practices
6. Singh, P. (2021): Impact of Non-Performing Assets on Bank Performance
7. Das, R. (2021): Growth of Retail Lending in Indian Banks
8. Nair, L. (2021): Agricultural Advances and Rural Credit Development
9. Chatterjee, P. (2021): Digitalization of Loan Processing Systems
10. Patel, H. (2022): Credit Monitoring Systems in Public Sector Banks
11. Kaur, J. (2022): Bank Credit and Women Entrepreneurship
12. Yadav, M. (2022): Technology-Based Credit Assessment Models
13. Sen, A. (2023): Loan Recovery through SARFAESI Act
14. Bhat, K. (2023): Risk-Based Loan Pricing Strategies
15. Menon, P. (2023): Importance of Loan Documentation
16. Bose, A. (2024): Early Warning Systems in Credit Monitoring
17. Mohan, L. (2024): Loan Recovery through Lok Adalats